

Molecular tools for zygotic embryo ablation in rice

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One of the serious constraints to hybrid rice technology adoption is the high cost of seed production. The dependence of hybrid seed production on parental crosses and the loss of heterotic vigor in successive generations can be eliminated if hybrid seeds can be multiplied asexually. Apomixis is an asexual means of seed production that occurs in several plant species including wild relatives of cereals such as maize, pearl millet, and wheat (Khush et al 1994). Careful searches made in rice germplasm so far have not revealed any occurrence of apomixis in rice (Rutger 1992, Brar et al 1995). Although several apomictic mechanisms exist, apomixis in principle is achieved by (1) cessation of steps leading to zygotic embryo development and (2) induction of an asexual embryo in nucellar tissue. Our goal is to develop apomictic rice through genetic engineering. In this note, we report the strategy and progress made in generating tools for arresting sexual embryo development.

The simplest way of arresting the development of the sexual embryo is to generate an inhibitory protein under the control of an egg- or zygote-specific promoter. Since such a promoter is to date not available in plants, we have taken a two-gene approach, which uses the *Cre-lox* recombination system (see figure). The *Cre* recombinase will be delivered through meiotic lineage to the zygote where it will excise the *lox* box intervening the coding region of a gene that can cause ablation (RNase, for example). Such a mechanism necessitates isolation of (1) a gene that is specifically expressed in meiotic cells and (2) a gene that is favorably expressed in the embryo but not in the embryo sac or endosperm. We have chosen *DMC1*, a meiosis-specific gene in yeast, and *REE5*, a 254-bp cDNA fragment that is accumulated in rice zygotic embryos (Kikuchi et al 1998).

Following a report that *DMC1* of *Arabidopsis* is meiosis-specific (Klimyuk and Jones 1997), we decided to isolate rice *DMC1* and test its expression pattern. We designed primers from partial rice Genebank sequence data (accession no.

U85613) and amplified a 417-bp rice genomic fragment that encodes *DMC1*. Nested-polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and Southern analyses suggested the presence of two rice *DMC1* genes. We isolated the two genes (*DMC1A* and *DMC1B*) from the IR64 bacterial artificial chromosome library and designed sequence-specific primers and probes to study their expression. Reverse transcriptase (RT)-PCR and Northern analyses revealed that both *DMC1A* and *DMC1B* are expressed in panicles at meiosis and in mitotically active tissues such as root tips and calli. Therefore, we conclude that rice *DMC1* genes are not meiosis-specific. We are currently exploring the potential utility of rice homologues of other yeast meiosis-specific genes such as *SPO11*.

REE5-specific PCR and Southern analyses indicated that the rice genome contains two *REE5* genes. By screening the IR36 genomic library, we isolated clones containing the two *REE5* genes. To isolate the *REE5* gene that is expressed during early embryogenesis, we performed 3' rapid amplification of cDNA ends (3' RACE) using spikelets at 2 d after fertilization. We then screened the genomic clones contain-

ing the two *REE5* genes using 3'-untranslated regions derived from the 3' RACE clone. Sequence analyses revealed that *REE5* encodes a novel phosphoprotein. We are currently studying the expression pattern of *REE5* genes using RT-PCR, Northern, and *in situ* hybridization techniques.

References

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A schematic diagram showing the constructs that can be used to derive an apomictic hybrid rice.